

A Dynamic Typology of Adjectives: Measurement Theory and Syntactic Interaction

Ling Sun

Indiana University, Bloomington IN 47405, USA
ls44@iu.edu

Abstract. Traditional degree semantics approaches have aimed to pin down the inherent and static class of adjectives. This paper presents a novel dynamic perspective, where the classification of an adjective is dynamic and syntactically dependent. Using measurement theory and fuzzy set analysis, the proposed framework defines dynamic patterns of adjective classes with a set of axioms and integrates these patterns with syntactic structures to explain the flexibility and constraints observed in adjectival expressions. Employing Mandarin data, the paper illustrates how different syntactic constructions select specific adjective classes, thereby affecting their interpretation and distribution. This approach not only accommodates cross-linguistic variations but also provides a more comprehensive understanding of the semantics of adjectives.

Keywords: Measurement theory · Adjective taxonomy · Fuzzy set.

1 Introduction

Measurement theory [7] has been discussed in the fuzzy set logic literature [1]. In the past decade, it has also been applied in formal semantic analysis of adjectival constructions: for instance, measure phrase distribution (e.g., *5 ft tall* vs. **5 lbs heavy*)[6], interadjective comparatives (e.g., *John is taller than Mary is smart*) [8], and differential comparatives (e.g., *5 inches taller*)[9].

This paper addresses two questions in the semantic research of adjectives: how to classify an adjective in one language and determine its syntactic distribution and interpretation. Instead of defining static classes, I propose a dynamic classification framework, adopting measurement theory taxonomy (section 2). This framework (1) defines the dynamic patterns of adjective classes with a set of axioms and scale shifting rules (section 3), and (2) associates syntactic structures with their selected adjective classes, which can accept or reject certain adjectives (section 4). While the paper primarily employs Mandarin data, the framework aims to account for universal generativities of adjectival expressions.

2 Syntactic Structures Can Change Adjective Scales

The class of an adjective can be dynamic and context-dependent. Precursors of such analysis include Sassoon (2010)[5], who argued that adjectives can result in either binary truth values or degrees, depending on the context.

Mandarin data provides an intriguing example. Unlike English, Mandarin features distinct syntactic constructions for non-gradable and gradable adjectives. As shown in (1), both *shi Adj de* and *hen Adj* in Mandarin can translate to *is Adj* in English. However, the non-gradable adjective *mutou* ‘wooden’ only appears with the construction *shi Adj de*, while *gao* ‘tall’ appears with *hen Adj*¹.

- (1) a. zhe zhang zhuozi shi {mutou/*gao} de
 this CL table be wood/tall de
 ‘This table is wooden/tall.’
 b. zhe zhang zhuozi hen {*mutou/gao}
 this CL table very wood/tall
 ‘This table is wooden/tall.’

Adjectives like *xin* ‘new’ break this pattern, as they are acceptable with both constructions (2a). Additionally, the interpretation differs between the two sentences (2b). In the former, *xin* ‘new’ indicates binary membership, where a secondhand book cannot be considered new. In the latter, it denotes graded membership, where the secondhand book can be relatively new compared to other secondhand books. This example showcases the dynamic gradability of the adjective *xin* ‘new’, regulated by different syntactic structures.

- (2) a. zhe ben shu {shi xin de/hen xin}
 this CL book {be new de/very new}
 ‘This book is new.’
 b. zhe ben ershou shu {*shi xin de/hen xin}
 this CL secondhand book {be new de/very new}
 ‘This secondhand book is new.’

Although this seems to suggest that adjectives can be flexible in terms of syntactic distribution and interpretations, not all adjectives fit with all constructions, as demonstrated in (1). This adaptive yet restricted distribution indicates that instead of a predefined adjective class, there is a class dynamic. An adjective can be associated with a dynamic yet constrained range of classes. Syntactic structures select a specific class, and if an adjective does not fit within this class, its use in the sentence will appear awkward.

3 Adjective Scales Dynamics

This section employs the taxonomy of measurement theory and the axioms of previous fuzzy set analysis [1]. It (1) presents a divergence between nominal and non-nominal adjectives in terms of truth value types (section 3.1), and (2) postulates two scale shift rules and three axioms to classify the different dynamics allowed across adjectives (section 3.1 and 3.2).

¹ *hen* ‘very’ is known as a bleached intensifier in predicative adjective constructions. This is discussed in more detail in section 4 with nominal scale expressions.

3.1 Nominal Scale: Axiom and Dynamics

The distinction between nominal and non-nominal adjectives, often referred to as gradable and non-gradable adjectives in formal semantics, is well-studied. Non-gradable adjectives typically reject intensifiers and comparatives [3]. In measurement theory, non-gradable adjectives correspond to nominal scales, while non-nominal scales (ordinal, interval, ratio) support gradability through graded membership and defined ordering. Nominal scales, however, define categories with binary membership rather than relations or ranks.

Axiom with Nominal Scale

The Distinctiveness Axiom is proposed for nominal scales. If met, it indicates that a nominal scale is available for the adjective, as defined below.

Distinctiveness Axiom: *is met iff for any x , if in some context C , $A_C(x) = 1$, then for all contexts, $A_C(x) = 1$.*

Consider the adjective *wooden*. It would be awkward to say a door is *wooden compared to this*, but not *wooden compared to that*, indicating that it meets the Distinctiveness Axiom and can access the nominal scale. Similarly, the adjective *new* implies a well-defined boundary when contrasted with *second-hand*. If *new* means ‘not existing before,’ an item is always *new* if it fits this criterion, rendering a binary truth value. However, *new* can also suggest gradient membership based on production or appearance time, leading to ambiguity between nominal and non-nominal meanings in English. This ambiguity is less pronounced in Mandarin due to syntactic effects, as shown already by example (2) in section 2.

Scale Shift between Nominal and Non-nominal Scales

The difference between nominal and non-nominal scales is fundamental. Nominal scales denote membership with a binary truth value (0 or 1) and defined boundaries, making them unfit for fuzzy set theory. Conversely, non-nominal scales exhibit gradient membership with multiple (non-binary) truth values.

Given the nature of truth values for nominal and non-nominal scales (binary vs. continuous), I propose a Contextual Membership Principle (CMP) to govern the dynamic shift between these scales, ensuring logically justified transitions.

Contextual Membership Principle (CMP): A change in the truth value type of an adjective is permissible if and only if one of the following conditions is met:

- *Nominal to Non-Nominal Shift:* If an adjective changes from nominal to non-nominal, there must be a contextual or lexical interpretation that induces gradient membership of the adjective (either through coercion or metaphor).
- *Non-Nominal to Nominal Shift:* If an adjective changes from non-nominal to nominal, there must be a context that supports a well-defined membership boundary.

When an adjective shifts from a nominal to a non-nominal scale, a means must be provided to interpret this gradient membership. This can be achieved through coercion, where a reinterpretation is forced, or through metaphor, where a new meaning is assigned to the adjective that allows for degrees. For example, the adjective *wooden* has a well-defined boundary, referring to things made of wood. Yet, when it shifts to a non-nominal scale, as in the metaphorical Mandarin usage referring to slow-witted individuals, or the English *a very wooden smell*, it implies a gradient membership. Similarly, the adjective *American*, which categorizes nationality with a binary truth value, can imply a gradient membership in *This Canadian is very American*.

Conversely, when an adjective shifts from a non-nominal scale to a nominal scale, the context must support a well-defined membership boundary. For instance, the adjective *tall* usually operates on a non-nominal scale, indicating various degrees of height. However, when comparing two entities, *tall* can shift to a nominal scale. The entity which is taller is classified as *tall*, creating a clear boundary between *tall* and *not tall*. The CMP ensures these shifts are justified, maintaining semantic coherence.

3.2 Non-nominal Scales: Axioms and Dynamics

Non-nominal scales include ordinal, interval, and ratio scales. All three assume inherent ordering and can be modeled by a membership function according to fuzzy set theory. This paper focuses on two axioms from previous approaches using fuzzy set theory [1] to differentiate among these scale types. It also proposes a scale shifting rule that governs the dynamic change of non-nominal scales.

This approach highlights how scale dynamics associated with adjectives can be influenced by perceptual, cultural, and linguistic factors, supporting both cross-linguistic commonalities and differences.

Axioms with Non-nominal Scales

Bilgiç and Türkşen (2000) [1] discuss the importance of two axioms in constraining fuzzy scale types: the Archimedean Axiom and the Bounded Axiom.

Archimedean Axiom is met iff for any $a, b \in A$ there exists a positive integer m such that $a^{(m)} \succ b$ where $a^{(m)}$ is recursively defined as $a^1 = a$, $a^{(m)} = a \oplus a^{(m-1)}$.

Bounded Axiom is met iff there exist u and e in A such that: for all $a \in A$, $u \succ e$, $u \succsim a$ and $a \succsim e$.

(cited from Bilgiç & Türkşen (2000) Appendix Definition 3[1])

Archimedean Axiom states that for any two elements a and b in a set A , you can find a positive integer m such that applying a recursive binary operation to a m times will exceed b . For example, if a is 1 foot and b is 10 feet, adding 1 foot repeatedly will eventually surpass 10 feet. If this axiom is accepted, it allows

for an interval scale where differences between elements can be meaningfully measured, though it lacks a true zero point.

Bounded Axiom states that there exist two elements, u and e , in a set A , where u is an upper bound and e is a lower bound. For example, in a set of heights, u could be the tallest height and e the shortest. If the lower bound is satisfied, a ratio scale becomes available, allowing for meaningful measurements with a true zero point, enabling comparisons of absolute magnitudes, such as height and weight. The relationship between the two axioms and the scales is summarized in Table 1.

Scale	Archimedean	Lower Bounded
Ordinal	–	–
Interval	+	–
Ratio	+	+

Table 1. Properties of Different Scales

The capacity of an adjective to satisfy the two axioms depends on three major factors:

1. **Perceptual Properties:** If an adjective denotes a mono-dimensional and visual property, visual stacking can support the Archimedean Axiom without relying on real numbers.
e.g., stacking lengths or heights visually is straightforward compared to stacking loudness levels.
2. **Cross-Cultural Influences:** A more industrialized culture, or specific occupations within a culture, can provide more real number measurement systems (such as inches, Fahrenheit, or Celsius) that support the Archimedean and Bounded Axioms. Real numbers can easily support recursive functions and sometimes include zero, facilitating precise measurements.
3. **Linguistic Integration:** The introduction of a measurement system to a society can lead to the creation or incorporation of new lexical items, resulting in cross-linguistic effects.
e.g., both *leng* ‘cold’ and *di* ‘low’ can describe perceptual temperature in Mandarin, but only *di* ‘low’ satisfies the Archimedean Axiom. In contrast, in English, both *cold* and *low* are acceptable for describing temperature differences, highlighting a cross-linguistic difference induced by lexical idiosyncrasy. This distinction is illustrated by the awkwardness of using *leng* ‘cold’ but the acceptability of *colder* in the following sentence:

- (3) $\text{j\bar{in}ti\bar{a}n\ b\bar{i}} \quad \text{zh\bar{o}us\bar{a}n} \quad \{*\textit{leng/d\bar{i}}\} \text{ w\bar{u} d\bar{u}.$
 today compare Wednesday $\{\textit{cold/low}\}$ 5 degrees.
 ‘Today(’s temperature) is 5 degrees $\{\textit{colder / lower}\}$ than Wednesday.’

Scale Shifting with Non-nominal Scales

This paper proposes a Hierarchical Precision Principle (HPP) to regulate the dynamic shift across non-nominal scale. The HPP licenses shift to a stronger

measurement scale if it can reduce fuzziness or be required for semantic coherence, provided that a stronger scale is available. In this hierarchy, ratio scales are considered stronger than interval scales, which in turn are stronger than ordinal scales. The availability of these scales is determined by the Archimedean Axiom and the Bounded Axiom, as detailed in the preceding section.

Hierarchical Precision Principle (HPP): a scale shift is permissible iff both of the conditions below are met:

- At least one stronger, more precise scale is available;
- The shift must reduce fuzziness of the proposition or is required by semantic coherence of the proposition.

For example, comparing happiness and height: using *shorter* with an interval scale (real numbers) reduces fuzziness compared to using an ordinal scale (perceptual order). Conversely, using *happier* remains fuzzy due to the lack of a real number scale. On the other hand, *very short* and *very happy* are equally fuzzy. Since the degree of shortness relative to an unspecified threshold is not fuzzier than height relative to that threshold, shifting from ordinal to interval is not justified. Therefore, *very short* remains as fuzzy as *very happy*. Additionally, if measure phrases (e.g., *5 ft*) are used, an ordinal scale becomes logically invalid, necessitating a shift to a stronger scale for semantic coherence (section 4).

4 Mandarin Case Study: Syntactic Structure and Scale Dynamics

This section applies the proposed dynamic scale approach to Mandarin, illustrating the framework’s predictions through type-based analysis. Despite focusing on Mandarin, the principles of scale dynamics (section 3) and semantic types here are applicable across languages, highlighting the framework’s universal relevance.

This paper discusses seven adjectival expressions, summarized below, along with their selected scale types in Table 2.

(4) a. Predication	<i>shi mutou de</i> is wooden de	‘is wooden’
b. Implicit Equative	<i>yiyang shi mutou de</i> same is wood de	‘are both wooden’
c. Bare Comparison	<i>bi ta gao</i> compare her tall	‘taller than her’
d. Explicit Equative	<i>yiyang gao</i> same tall	‘equally tall’
e. Intensifier	<i>hen gao</i> very tall	‘very tall’
f. Differential Comparative	<i>gao 5 mi</i> tall 5 meter	‘5 meter taller’

- g. Measure phrase modification *5 mi gao* ‘5 m tall’
5 m tall

Sentence Type	Scale	Adj Type
Predication Implicit Equative	Nominal	$\langle e, t_{\in\{0,1\}} \rangle$
Bare Comparison Explicit Equative Intensifier	Ordinal	$\langle e, t_{\in[0,1]} \rangle$
Differential Comparative	Interval	$\langle e, d \rangle$
Measure Phrase Modification	Ratio	$\langle e, 1 \rangle$

Table 2. Scale selected by different sentence types in Mandarin

Nominal Scale expression in Mandarin, unlike English, receive different syntactic markings compared to non-nominal expressions (see section 2). The following formalizations demonstrate how these markings select scale types: *shi* ‘is’ selects a binary truth value, while *feichang* ‘extremely’ selects a continuous truth value.

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket shi \rrbracket &= \lambda G_{\langle e, t_{\in\{0,1\}} \rangle} . \lambda x . G(x) \\ \llbracket feichang \rrbracket &= \lambda G_{\langle e, t_{\in[0,1]} \rangle} . \lambda x . G^2(x) \end{aligned}$$

To accommodate both binary and continuous truth values, I adopt a dynamic truth value evaluation model.² In this framework, a proposition is true if its evaluation is a member of the set T_{pos} . For nominal scale predicates, a membership evaluation is true (binary). For non-nominal predicates, the degree to which the entity fits the predicate must exceed a threshold τ , which may vary across individuals.

$$T_{pos} = \begin{cases} \{1\} & \text{if } t \text{ is binary} \\ \{t | t \gtrsim \tau\} & \text{if } t \text{ is continuous} \end{cases}$$

Additionally, a power term is associated with intensifiers that reflects their hierarchical order (e.g., *super* > *very* > NULL > *slightly* in English). Higher power indicates a higher rank in the intensifier hierarchy and increases the slope of the measurement function. Studies have shown such effects [2].³

Take Mandarin *mutou* ‘wooden’ and *xin* ‘new’ as example. The former only renders a binary truth value (nominal scale), and, according to Contextual Membership Principle (CMP), when forced with non-nominal scales, a metaphoric meaning is forced (*mu* ‘slow-witted’) with a change of linguistic form (reduction of second syllable). For *xin* ‘new’, it is ambiguous between binary versus continuous truth value. The dynamics of the two with relevant expressions are shown in the table below.

² There are well-developed methods for representing multiple truth values (e.g., possible worlds, modality). For simplicity, this paper uses the current denotation, which should be compatible with other models of multiple truths.

³ The bleached intensifier *hen* in Mandarin is likely due to fewer intensifier hierarchies (*feichang* ‘super’ > *hen* ‘very’ > *youdian* ‘slightly’), where *hen* has a power of 1.

	<i>mutou/mu</i>	<i>xin</i>
Predication	<i>mutou/*mu</i> ‘wooden’	‘not existing before’
Intensifier	<i>*mutou/mu</i> ‘slow-witted’	‘recently’

Table 3. Dynamics of adjectives with predication and intensifier

Ordinal Scale expressions, including bare comparatives, explicit equatives, and intensifiers, may undergo scale shifts as regulated by the Hierarchical Precision Principle (HPP). For bare comparatives, comparing two real number-defined degrees (interval) eliminates the fuzziness of comparing two perceptual values (ordinal). Since no fuzziness remains at interval scale, a shift to a ratio scale is blocked, as it cannot further reduce fuzziness. For adjectives combined with *COMP* morpheme—silent in Mandarin but realized in English (e.g., -er)—a precede or greater than relation is formed, depending on the available scale.

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket \text{Adj-COMP} \rrbracket &= \lambda y. \lambda x. A(x) \ggg A(y), \ggg := \begin{cases} > & \text{if } A_{(e,d)} \\ \succ & \text{if } A_{(e,t \in [0,1])} \end{cases} \\ \llbracket yiyang \rrbracket &= \lambda A. \lambda S. \exists v \in T. [x \in S \rightarrow A(x) = v] \end{aligned}$$

For equatives, comparing real number degrees reduces fuzziness, but fuzziness remains, as equatives indicate that the degrees to which the entities equally hold is positive. The threshold for positivity is fuzzy (failing the Bounded Axiom). A ratio scale can eliminate this fuzziness by providing a defined lower boundary. The morpheme *yiyang* ‘same’ takes an adjective and a set of entities, indicating that there is a positive value such that all evaluations of x for A are equal to the value. For nominal scales, the value is binary, rendering implicit comparatives (e.g., both wooden). For ordinal scales, the value is a continuous (e.g., equally new), rendering explicit comparatives. The fuzziness of explicit comparatives is reduced with HPP application, where changing the scale to interval results in a degree above the contextual threshold (e.g., equally short), and changing to ratio results in an interval with a positive size (e.g., equally tall).

HPP Application: If HPP is applied, then the continuous truth value t is overridden by the stronger scale, reducing fuzziness. Specifically:

- If shifted to ratio scale, t is saturated by 1 and $t > \tau$ set to $|1| > 0$.
- If shifted to interval scale, t is saturated by d and τ mapped to degree threshold θ .

Consider the adjectives *gaoxing* ‘happy’, *ai* ‘short’, and *gao* ‘tall’ in Mandarin. *Gaoxing* ‘happy’ is associated with an ordinal scale, *ai* ‘short’ with an interval scale, and *gao* ‘tall’ with a ratio scale. Their interpretations in relevant expressions are shown in Table 4. All adjectives with intensifiers remain fuzzy with an ordinal scale. For bare comparatives, *gaoxing* ‘happy’ denotes perceptual ordering, while *ai* ‘short’ and *gao* ‘tall’ compare the heights of two entities. For equatives, *ai* ‘short’ indicates that the set of entities are all short and of the same height, while *gao* ‘tall’ indicates that the set of entities are of the same height without specifying if they are tall or not. This quality found in *short* but not *tall* is termed ‘evaluativity’ in previous literature[4].

	<i>gaoxing</i>	<i>ai</i>	<i>gao</i>
Bare Comp.	$A(x) \succ A(y)$	$A(x) > A(y)$	$A(x) > A(y)$
Explicit Equa.	$A(x) = t$	$A(x) = d$	$A(x) = \tau$
Intensifier	$A^e(x) \succ \tau$	$A^e(x) \succ \tau$	$A^e(x) \succ \tau$

Table 4. Interpretation of adjectives with bare comparative, explicit equative, and intensifier

Interval & Ratio Scale expressions accept only adjectives that can access these scales, leading to a highly constrained distribution of adjectives. Consider again *gaoxing* ‘happy’, *ai* ‘short’, and *gao* ‘tall’. Since the strongest scale associated with them are ordinal, interval, and ratio respectively, their distribution across relevant expressions is shown in the table below.

	<i>gaoxing</i>	<i>ai</i>	<i>gao</i>
Diff. Comp.			*
MP modification		*	*

Table 5. Distribution of adjectives with differential comparative and measure phrase (MP) modification

According to the Archimedean Axiom, a measure phrase is meaningful only on an interval or stronger scale, where units of differences are defined. A possible type-based analysis of measure phrases *5 ft* is as below, where it takes an interval as argument and is true if the interval’s size is 5 ft. This implies that only intervals can combine with measure phrases. A *DIFF* morpheme is further proposed that, when combined with an adjective, results in a closed interval from $A(x)$ to $A(y)$. In Mandarin, this morpheme is realized as *chu*, as in *gao chu *(5 ft)* ‘5 ft taller’.

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket 5 \text{ ft} \rrbracket &= \lambda I. |I| = 5 \text{ ft} \\ \llbracket \text{Adj-DIFF} \rrbracket &= \lambda y. \lambda x. [A(x) - A(y)] \end{aligned}$$

Notably, these two scales are regulated by the two axioms that are subject to lexical idiosyncrasies (section 3.2), leading to significant cross-linguistic variation. For instance, *heavy* in English does not satisfy the Bounded Axiom, unlike Mandarin *zhong* ‘heavy’. Consequently, measure phrase modification with *heavy* is acceptable in Mandarin but not in English (*5 bang zhong* ‘*5 lbs heavy’).

5 Conclusion

By leveraging measurement theory and fuzzy set analysis, this paper has demonstrated how syntactic structures can dynamically interact with adjectives scales, shaping the distribution and interpretation of adjectives among these expressions. While the focus is on Mandarin, the paper argues that the principles of scale dynamics and the type-based compositional analysis are applicable to other languages. This broader applicability is supported by discussing potential cross-linguistic variations and the universal relevance of the proposed framework as a robust theoretical tool. Future research can extend this approach to other languages.

Bibliography

- [1] Bilgiç, T., Türkşen, I.B.: Measurement of membership functions: theoretical and empirical work. In: *Fundamentals of fuzzy sets*, pp. 195–227. Springer (2000)
- [2] Hersh, H.M., Caramazza, A.: A fuzzy set approach to modifiers and vagueness in natural language. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General* **105**(3), 254 (1976)
- [3] Kennedy, C.: Comparatives, semantics of. *Concise Encyclopedia of Philosophy of Language and Linguistics* pp. 68–71 (2004)
- [4] Rett, J.: Antonymy and evaluativity. In: *Semantics and Linguistic Theory*. vol. 17, pp. 210–227 (2007)
- [5] Sassoon, G.W.: The degree functions of negative adjectives. *Natural language semantics* **18**(2), 141–181 (2010)
- [6] Sassoon, G.W.: Measurement theory in linguistics. *Synthese* **174**(1), 151–180 (2010)
- [7] Stevens, S.S.: Measurement, statistics, and the schemapiric view. *Science* **161**(3844), 849–856 (1968)
- [8] Van Rooij, R.: Measurement and interadjective comparisons. *Journal of Semantics* **28**(3), 335–358 (2011)
- [9] Zhang, L., Ling, J.: The semantics of comparatives: A difference-based approach. *Journal of Semantics* **38**(2), 249–303 (2021)